

The Degree of Possessing Media Education skills among Classroom Student-Teachers at Yarmouk University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 04, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Degree of Possessing; Practical Education Female Students; Classroom Teachers; Yarmouk University; Media Education.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4494685</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to reveal the degree to which female students of practical education, specializing in class teacher, at Yarmouk University possess media education skills. The descriptive method was adopted, and the study population consisted of all students of practical education in the classroom specialization at Yarmouk University, who were registered for the first semester of the academic year 2019-2020; Their number reached (115) students. All were chosen as an intentional sample for the study. The questionnaire was used, it consisted of two parts: the section dealing with the variables of the study, which is the branch of the General Certificate of Secondary Education, the type of school in which the student would apply, and the student's GPA. The second part of questionnaire included (19) paragraphs to measure the degree of students 'possession of media education skills. The results of the study showed that the degree of students 'possession of media education skills was average, and there were statistically significant differences in the variable of the general secondary certificate for female students in favor of the certificate branch (scientific), also the existence of differences in the school variable in which the student applied in favor of (private) schools, and the existence of differences On the variable of the cumulative average of the student in favor of the (accepted) average holders. The study recommended the necessity to propose a national media education plan that includes universities and Jordanian schools.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Media education has become one of the topics that resonate in the field of education with the aim of educating students in order to understand the things that surround them with their different dimensions, how to adapt and live with them and understand the requirements of the modern era, and prepare students to face the diverse and accelerated events that impose themselves on various aspects of life, including the field of education in general and teaching in particular (Aljawarneh & Atan, 2018). The development of communication supersedes with the digital information revolution has led to a change in the type and shape of communication mechanisms (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). This led to the existence of different sources of information, and the book or teacher are no longer the only major sources (Alsafadi et al., 2020). However, the media in all its forms has become a strong competitor to the teacher in providing students with knowledge and information, which has become an impact on students cognitively, socially, healthy, culturally and in various aspects (Yahya, 2007).

Both media and education play a key role in shaping student culture, based on the role and community objective that adults and young people, including young or young students, seek to become positive in their lives and within their communities (Al-Omari et al., 2020). The dialectic of education with the media is not limited to the impact of its media on students, especially young ones, but also about how they deal with what the media offers (Al-Shair, 2007).

Based on this, the importance of having a systematic and structured media educational space to counter the negative effects of the multiplicity of media sources to which students are exposed is demonstrated, as this space is reflected through the ability of teachers to practice media education skills, which seek to properly shape the personality of students, in terms of giving them the ability to choose the appropriate media content and rationally criticize it rationally, leading to their growth of a balanced, integrated and non-extremist growth in all aspects of their personalities.

The concept of media education emerged in the late 1960s and evolved in the 1970s as a defense project aimed at protecting children and young people from the dangers created by the media, focusing on exposing inappropriate values to society, and the need to reject them and keep them away from them, and media education sought to enable students to detect false messages, provide them with the skills of selecting and participating in the handling of information, in order to effectively understand the media culture that surrounds them (Yahya, 2007).

The students dealt with the huge amount of media messages on the basis of which their understanding of the world around them is formed to make media education an urgent necessity, the student receives, analyzes, discusses and

evaluates the media message according to the factors and personal needs of the self and the system of values that control his behavior and orientation, and this leads to different interpretations among students about the single media message (Alshare et al., 2020). and accordingly, media education aims to enable students to reach the skills that link media messages from different sources, and skills of reading, writing, talking and dialogue that enable them to communicate (Mahafzah et al., 2020). Effective, respect for cultural specificities within the framework of generalities and other cultural variables (Khatib, 2007).

Several definitions of the concept of media education have been mentioned (Brown, 2008:103) as "a method used to demonstrate the skills and abilities of university students that require awareness of advanced education in modern communications, such as e-learning and multimedia in the information society". He defines it (Al-Shamimari, 2010:20) as "enabling community members to gain an understanding of the communication media used in their society, and the way they work, and thus enable them to acquire skills in using the media to understand others."

(Share, 2015:119) defined it as "gaining the knowledge, understanding and proper application of skills and attitudes that allow students to deal with the complex and changing media world in a conscious and purposeful way, and to gain the ability to use the media in an active and dynamic manner for effective social participation." It is also known as "deepening the awareness of individuals about traditional and digital media and enabling them to understand and correctly judge their contents by learning the knowledge and technical skills necessary for it" (Salem and Radi, 2018: 44).

Media education skills are summarized in three main skills: analysis, media message through informed dialogue, careful understanding and distance from subjectivity (Alomari et al., 2020). The skill of research is the ability to find additional sources around the media message of interest. The ability to change the impact of media messages (Al-Saleh, 2007), as well as to give students the skills to decode the media message, critical thinking about the content of the media material, decision-making on this content, and the production or participation of media programs (Al-Jawarneh, 2016). There is an integral relationship between the various media education skills (Al-Khairi, 2009).

It should be noted that school media education is influenced by various factors, including: erroneous understanding of the role of educational media (Al-Da'abseh, et al., 2018). poor communication between the departments of the educational process to achieve media education, lack of scientific methods in media education, poor planning of this type of education, lack of specialized educational media staff, as well as the influence of media education on political, economic and social aspects (Al-Shodifat and Al-Khasawneh, 2012).

Media education in schools is also achieved through several methods, the most important of which are: formulating and defining the objectives of media education in accordance with the objectives of the educational phase, (Al-Omari et al., 2018). adopting media education as a subject within the subjects of the curriculum (Alzoubi et al., 2020). preparing media education programs in partnership with specialists in media and education, employing student activities to achieve the objectives of media education, and must have the availability of material resources, the rehabilitation of teachers, the dissemination of media education culture in schools, the work of school media channels that enable students to participate and express opinions, and enable students who are distinguished in media education to meet their colleagues. From Arab and foreign countries to share knowledge, skills and experiences (Diop, 2011; Beghily, 2008).

Despite the growing interest in school media education in many countries, including Jordan, it continues to suffer from many problems, in terms of what it is, its objectives and mechanisms, making it blurred in the minds of its practitioners and non-practitioners (Ministry of Culture, 2020). Based on the above, the current study reveals the degree to which female students of practical education have the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for school media education skills (Aljawarneh & Al-Omari, 2018).

The diversity of media resources to which students are exposed has multiple effects, all of which are involved in shaping their value system, (Banyhamdan et al., 2020). which sometimes contradicts the values of the family and society, where students in the first three grades are considered to be the most affected group according to their level of awareness and the ease of being led behind what the different media offer (al-Bourini et al., 2020)., especially in the absence of their inability to distinguish between the original and the outsider of their society (Alwagfi et al., 2020). or to distinguish between falsehood and reality, as what the media offers in an interesting and attractive way (Masa'd & Aljawarneh, 2020).

The problem of the study also highlights the fact that the feature of the current era is dominated by the wide and rapid exchange of cultures and values between societies, and that the media content has become a cultural mix that has an impact on young people, especially young learners, as the media message appeals to them through entertainment, social, animation and other programs. As well as electronic media, communication through its pages, and the use of smartphone programs, which challenge the culture of students, where students fall between responding to what these means offer with their different effects negatively and positively, and between the cultural and moral system of society and family.

Therefore, the practice of teachers in the first three grades of media education skills in light of the reality of the current media explosion is essential in their work and not an educational luxury; Question 1: "What degree of practical education students have the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for school media education skills from their point of view?" Question 2: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance

($\alpha=0.05$) in the degree of ownership of the students of practical education the teacher specializes in the skills of school media education from their point of view in the light of variables: the branch of the high school certificate, the type of school in which the student is applied, and the cumulative rate of the student.

The importance of the current study lies in its approach to the subject of school media education, which is supposed to be given to students in light of the increasing proliferation of different media and to face the negative effects of it. The importance of the study also stems in determining the extent to which student's teachers possess media education skills that will be reflected on their students in the classroom, in terms of giving students appropriate media education skills and protecting them from negative and false ideas offered by some media outlets. The importance of this study also stems from the importance of the target group of students, namely the students who are teachers for the first three grades, as this stage of study is the cornerstone of the building of the personalities of young students. The results of this study can be used by decision makers in universities and the Ministry of Higher Education through the development of a university course specializing in providing students with media education skills.

2. Literature Review

Through a review of previous studies related, researchers found some Arab and foreign studies that focused on the subject of media education, including: In a study conducted by Al-Khazala (2020) aimed to identify the degree to which students of Al-Bayt University possess media education skills in light of some variables in Jordan, and to achieve the objectives of the study, the selection of a sample of (420) students studying at al-Bayt University was selected in a simple random way, and used the descriptive survey method, to achieve the objectives of the study and was designed to determine its sincerity and consistency. The results of the study reached that the degree of ownership of the students of al-Bayt University for media education skills came to an average degree on the study tool as a whole, and the results of the study also showed the existence of statistically significant differences attributable to the sex variable and for the benefit of male students, and the existence of statistically significant differences attributable to the change of the faculty and for the benefit of the scientific colleges, and the existence of statistical lying differences attributable to the change of the year study and for the benefit of the fourth year, and recommended the need for the development of a specialized university course in media education that is mandatory for all university students.

In a study conducted by Methanani and Ibrahim (2019), it aimed to reveal the effectiveness of educational media and its messages in the development of students' personal and life skills (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). The descriptive approach and survey method have been adopted. High school students were selected as a research community. The research was applied to a sample of 500 students, along with a sample of secondary school media supervisors of 33 supervisors. The results of the research showed statistically significant differences in the role of educational media in the development of personal skills among secondary school students. It is attributable to the sex variable in favour of females, and there are no differences attributable to the specialty variable.

In a study conducted by Al-Ja'ad and Al-Asri (2018), the aim was to find out the reality of the contribution of middle school teachers to the media education of female students, and related to the development of the ethics of access to media messages, writing them, developing critical skills, and identifying the obstacles that hinder female teachers in applying media education to middle school students. The study adopted the descriptive (survey) approach and questionnaire as a study tool, and was distributed to a sample of the 519 middle school teachers in Riyadh. The study found the need to prepare female students to deal with different media to develop the entry skills of media messages, warn them of certain media outlets that affect religion, morality and national belonging, and encourage them to take advantage of national media, which highlights its importance in educating the student to commit to the desired moral values, such as honesty, honesty and rights preservation, as well as attention to media education at the higher levels (interactive application level) of criticism, analysis and evaluation.

A study was conducted by Al-AdlyTawlaba, and Karasana in (2018) to investigate the impact of the development of educational units in media education in the light of media education in the books of national and civic education for the basic stage and to measure its impact on the development of media awareness among students. The study community is a tenth-grade student in the schools of the Kasbah Irbid Directorate; the sample of the study consisted of two experimental and female divisions, and a measure of media awareness was designed to measure the impact of the development unit in the development of media awareness among female students. The results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences in the awareness was designed to measure the impact of the development unit in the development of media awareness among female students. The results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences in the awareness of the students due to the units developed in the light of media education in the books of national and civic education, and the researchers recommended work to develop a national vision planned for media education systematic within the curriculum.

In a study carried out by Abdel Hamid (2019) aimed to know the level of media education skills among university youth, and the relationship of media education to the system of education received by young people, which varies between the systems of scientific studies and theory and government and private education in The

Governorate of Cairo, used the method of qualitative and comparing method, where the discussions of the group focused on a sample of young people in four private and governmental universities, a sample of (88) students, were compared their use of new media and their analytical and critical skills, and the study reached the ability of students of the colleges to apply theory to the application of theory. Some media education skills when dealing with the new media at a higher level than students of practical colleges in public or private universities, and it was generally noted that all students in the study sample needed a lot of awareness about media education and skills.

In a study conducted by Fedorov&Levitskaya, (2016), which aimed to identify students' perceptions of media education and their level of motivation, the study sample consisted of 100 randomly selected students, and the questionnaire was used to collect study data. The results of the study showed that the perceptions of students in universities about media education were positive, that their level of motivation was high, and that there are no statistically significant differences in students' perceptions about media education and their level of competence due to the gender of the student or his level of study.

Fleming (2014) conducted a study aimed at finding out how faculty members deal with the Media Education Course in the United States of America, including (277) teachers who were asked questions about the extent to which their students possessed media education skills and processed their elements, the results of the study showed teachers believed that their students were more efficient about media access (access to the media (access to the web, tv programmers, the use of video games, the skill of writing messages (creating a web page, writing a material for electronic or printing, and less efficient analysis of web-content analysis and television content. Advertising and music) and the study indicated a relationship between the age of the teacher and his years of teaching and his perceptions of the skills of media education among their students, calling for the inclusion of new media in seminars on media education.

Schmidt (2013) A study aimed at conducting an analysis of the media education approach in the Journalism Department of the University of Stony Brook, in the United States, where the researcher collected materials related to the curriculum of visual and audio documents and lectures, conducting interviews with (28) people among administrative supervisors, lecturers, trainers, journalists, bachelor's students, graduate students and assistant teachers, and the results showed that media education taught students how to obtain, evaluate, analyses and evaluate the type of news, and that students became regularly following the news and became more aware of the media after their studies of the curriculum.

3. Methodology

The study community is made up of all students of practical education in the specialization of the teacher of the class at Yarmouk University, registered in the first semester of the academic year 2019-2020 and numbered (115) and all of them students according to the records of the Office of Practical Education at Yarmouk University. They were all selected as a intended sample of the study as they completed the theoretical courses or were about to finish them and began to apply in practice, and therefore in the field of education as classes and in their last or penultimate semester, and table (1) shows the distribution of the study sample members according to its variables.

Table 1: The distribution of the study sample members according to its variables

Variables	Category	Number	Percentage
High School Certificate Branch	Scientific	50	%48
	Literary	55	%52
The type of school in which the student is applied	Government	54	%51
	Especially	51	%49
Cumulative rate	Excellent	17	%16
	Very good	30	%29
	Good	39	%37
	Acceptable	19	%18

To verify the authenticity of the tool, it actually measures what it was designed to measure; In its initial form, the tool consisted of (27) paragraphs each paragraph that is indicative of one of the skills of media education. The arbitrators were asked to express their opinion in terms of the composition of the paragraphs on the subject of the study, their validity and their relevance to what was prepared for them. After the arbitration, a linguistic

adjustment was made for five paragraphs, two paragraphs were cancelled and five paragraphs were added. In the light of the views of the arbitrators, the final resolution is composed of 30 paragraphs.

To ensure that the study tool is stable, the test in method was used, based on Pearson's correlation factor, on a survey sample of (10) female students, where the sample was not included in the study sample. The results showed a high correlation between the two applications, with a two-week time difference, with a correlation coefficient of 0.89. In light of the indications of honesty and consistency, the researchers believe that the tool is suitable for the current study.

4. Results

Results of question 1:

Answer to the first question: "How do students of practical education have the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for school media education skills? To answer this question, mathematical circles and standard deviations of sample responses were extracted on the degree to which students of practical education have the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for school media education skills. The answers are arranged downwards, and the degree of possession for each paragraph is determined, as shown in table (2).

Table 2: Mathematical circles and standard deviations to the degree of ownership of media education skills by Yarmouk University students ranked downwardly according to the value of the arithmetic medium for each paragraph.

Number	Rank	Paragraph	Average	SD	Class
11	1	I distinguish between rumor and truth in media messages	2.68	.760	High
7	2	I can criticize the media material	2.56	.368	High
3	3	I can understand the media stuff	2.54	.438	High
9	4	I establish the credibility of the source of the information	2.51	.521	High
5	5	I'm able to analyze the media material	2.47	.745	High
16	6	I can share the media material with my colleagues or others	2.44	.569	High
2	7	Use available information effectively	2.39	.546	High
25	8	The media material is well established negatively or positively	2.35	.587	High
28	9	I'm taking advantage of the media to know the reality.	2.34	.552	High
23	10	I determine the targeted and constructive media messages.	2.31	.529	Medium
13	11	I'm making the right decision about the media stuff.	2.28	.574	Medium
1	12	I can easily access the required information.	2.22	.623	Medium
24	13	Accurately analyze visual messages	2.16	.615	Medium
19	14	I can hold training workshops for my students related to promoting their media education	2.11	.705	Medium
12	15	I take into account the moral aspect in dealing with different media materials	2.08	.668	Medium
15	16	I can participate in the production of media materials	2.05	.716	Medium
20	17	Avoid non-targeted media content.	2.01	.637	Medium
27	18	I accept the different opinions expressed through the media without intolerance	1.98	.721	Medium
14	19	I understand what the different media message is about..	1.92	.658	Medium
17	20	Publish media messages through different media.	1.84	.466	Medium
29	21	I recognize what students need in the first grades of media materials	1.81	.512	Medium
22	22	Criticizing the non-purposeful media material in a meaningful and objective way	1.76	.661	Medium

10	23	Determine the target group of different media messages	1.73	.436	Medium
16	24	I can share the media material with my colleagues or others	1.71	.338	Medium
30	25	I enhance the skill of expressing through the media within the rules of literature	1.69	.402	Medium
26	26	Determine the impact of the media article on the social values of students	1.67	.386	Medium
18	27	I determine the appropriate language that corresponds to the news or information when I want to comment through different means of communication	1.65	.407	Low
8	28	Avoid media material that is not in line with social values	1.62	.513	Low
21	29	I follow the various media in an orderly manner that doesn't waste my time	1.60	.423	Low
4	30	I employ the media to address students' problems	1.58	.492	Low
The total			2.06	.552	Medium

Table (2) shows that the computational range ranged from (2.68-1.58) too high to low, while the standard deviation ranged from (0.760-0.492), while the arithmetic medium of the instrument as a whole was (2.06) and average, with a standard deviation of (0.552), paragraph (11) which states that "I distinguish between rumor and truth in media messages" has a high account of (2.86) and a high score, while paragraph 4, which states "I employ the media to deal with student problems", has obtained a "media profile" of 1.58 and a degree Low. This may be due to the in qualification of female students during their school and university studies, as there are no special subjects taught to students as a curriculum or even as part of a study subject, which confirms the need to introduce media education as a subject taught in Jordanian schools and universities; Social studies, such as a study (Khazala, 2020).

This is also confirmed by the results of the study carried out by Bouden and Labza (2018), in which they stressed the need to learn and teach about the media, not through them, as well as the study of Al-Amiri and Al-Maqati (2018) also revealed a serious decline in the inclusion of social studies books for media concepts, meanwhile the Magari Study (2017) stressed the need to include media education in the Palestinian curriculum, in addition to several studies (Mohammed, 2012; Mikhaleva, 2015), which stressed the urgent need to include media education in the curriculum, both at school and university.

Results of question 2: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of ownership of the female students of practical education the teacher's specialization in the field of educational skills in the field of education in light of the variables of the branch of the high school certificate, the type of school in which the student is applied, and the cumulative rate.

First: The branch of the high school certificate to find out the effect of the variable branch of the high school certificate has been extracted mathematical averages and standard deviations, as well as tests (T), as shown in table (3).

Table 3: T-Test on the level of the main study tool areas by variable branch of high school certificate (scientific, literary)

Scale	High School	Number	Average	SD	T	P
The degree of ownership of practical education students is the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for the skills of school media education	Scientific	50	2.01	.551	2.549	.012
	Literary	55	1.93	.366		

The table shows statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample members in favour of the scientific branch category.

Table (3) shows statistically significant differences at the level of indication ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample members in favour of the scientific branch category, where the specialization variable (scientific

branch) received a medium average of (2.01) and a medium degree, while the specialization variable (literary branch) received an average of (1.93) and also a medium degree. This may be due to the fact that the education system in Jordan distributes students at the end of the basic and secondary level depending on the student's average in the last grade of the basic level; This result was contradicted by the result of the Study of Methanani and Ibrahim (2019), which showed no statistically significant differences on the variable specialization.

Second: The type of school in which the student is applied to see the effect of the variable type of school in which the student is applied has been extracted mathematical averages and standard deviations, as well as tests (T), as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Test (t) on the paragraphs of the study tool by variable type of school in which the student is applied (government, private)

Scale	School type	Number	Average	SD	T	p
The degree of ownership of practical education students is the specialization of the teacher at Yarmouk University for the skills of school media education	Government	54	1.69	.398	8.224	.000
	Privet	51	2.02	.474		

The table shows statistically significant differences at the indicative level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the responses of sample members according to the school type variable; and for the benefit of private schools, where the government school variable received a mathematical medium of (1.69) while the private school variable received a mathematical medium of (2.02). This may be because private schools focus on guiding students through media messages and their activities through school radio and through read and video messages to students and their parents. The result of this study was in agreement with a study carried out by Al-Shodifat and Al-Khasawneh (2012), the results of which showed that the level of media education in private schools in Jordan is high.

Third: The cumulative rate of the effect of the cumulative rate variable of female students was extracted standard deviations and mathematical circles, as shown in table (5).

Table 5: Calculation averages and standard deviations of study tool paragraphs by GPI variable

Rate	Number	Average	SD
Excellent	17	1.90	.397
Very good	30	1.85	.341
Good	39	2.09	.539
Acceptable	19	1.83	.448
Total	105	1.92	.461

Table (5) Shows a virtual variation of the paragraphs of the study tool according to the GPA single-indication analysis (ANOVA) was conducted to determine the effect of the cumulative rate on the variable, so a degree of ownership of the degree of practical education students specializing in the teacher of the class at Yarmouk University for school media education skills, as shown in table (6).

Table 6: ANOVA analysis of the cumulative rate effect on the degree of ownership of media education skills

Source of variance	Total squares	Degrees of freedom	Average squares	F	P
Between groups	5.716	3	1.981	9.211	.000
Within groups	86.020	101	.204		
Total	91.784	104			

Table (6) shows statistically significant differences at the indication level ($\alpha =0.05$) in the responses of study sample members to the paragraphs of their instrument, so dimensional comparisons were made to identify these differences according to the LSD method, as shown in the table (7).

Table 7: LSD dimensional comparisons

Cumulative Rate A	Cumulative rate B	The difference between the averages	p
Excellent	Very good	-.043	.509
	Good	.038	.607

	Acceptable	-.241	.000
Very good	Excellent	.045	.513
	Good	.079	.211
	Acceptable	-.202	.001
Good	Excellent	-.034	.601
	Very good	-.080	.215
	Acceptable	-.280	.000
Acceptable	Excellent	.241	.000
	Very good	.201	.001
	Good	.279	.000

Table (7) shows statistically significant differences at the level of indication ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the cumulative rates (excellent, very good, and good) on the one hand and the other between the rate (acceptable), where the differences in favor of the category of female students with the rate were acceptable. This result may be due to the fact that female students with an (acceptable) grade may spend more time using different means of communication than female students with a grade (excellent, very, good) who spend more time studying and pursuing different study requirements; This result may also be interpreted on the basis that female students with an acceptable degree have become more aware and distinguished by what is published through the media as a result of their frequent use of these means and may therefore become more capable of distinguishing between reality and fiction, which has been reflected in their ability to present this skill to their students. The result of the current study agreed with AbdelHamid's study (2019) that most students need to enhance their media awareness, not just a specific group.

5. Recommendations

Through the results of this study, the researchers recommend the following: The need to propose a national plan for media education that includes Jordanian schools and universities. Include media education in the curriculum, whether at school or university. The Faculty of Education at Yarmouk University should publish media education by adding a study material in the study plan for students in general. The need to provide students with learning and education about the media, not just through them. Focus on training workshops and forums in universities and schools that enable students to possess and apply media education skills within the framework of different generalities and cultural variables.

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